

Valorization of food waste into renewable fuels via anaerobic digestion and inline CO₂ reforming over Ni-based catalysts

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ABSTRACT

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a promising technology for converting food waste (FW) or other biodegradable organic waste (BOW) into renewable biogas, while dry reforming of methane (DRM) is an environmentally friendly route for converting greenhouse gases into syngas. Moreover, the use of renewable biogas in dry reforming aligns with the global sustainability goals for reducing reliance on fossil fuels in producing important chemicals. In this regard, the present study deals with the valorization of food waste into renewable hydrogen/syngas by integrating AD and DRM. AD of FW was carried out in a lab-scale anaerobic reactor and the resulting biogas was passed over a sorption bed for H₂S removal. It was shown that iron hydroxide-based materials can effectively remove H₂S, thereby providing a clean biogas feed suitable for catalytic dry reforming. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that the Ni catalyst, doped with a small amount of noble metal and supported on Mg–Al mixed oxides, exhibits superior catalytic performance in reforming of real or model biogas mixtures. The catalyst showed outstanding stability despite online changes in the reaction parameters. This study may provide new insights toward the development of sustainable processes that simultaneously reduce BOW and CO₂, while also generating valuable products.

1. Introduction

The past 70 years have seen unprecedented growth in the global population, rapid urbanization and development of social economies, along with significant advancement in living standards. Consequently, there has been an unparalleled rise in energy demand, accompanied by an exponential increase in the municipal solid waste (MSW) generation as well as CO₂ emissions [1,2]. In 2016, the global MSW production was estimated at 2.01 billion metric tons per year, with projections indicating an increase to 2.2 billion tons by 2025 and over 3.4 billion tons by 2050 [3,4]. Current waste treatment methods are struggling to keep up with the growing rates of waste generation, as well as increasingly stringent environmental regulations on hazardous gas emissions. However, as waste generation and emissions continue to rise, the limitations of conventional waste management practices become more apparent,

indicating the need for innovative and sustainable solutions to address the problems. A promising solution for reducing both the fraction of MSW (including plastic and biodegradable waste) and CO₂ is to utilize them as feedstocks for producing fuels and chemicals (e.g. biogas, hydrogen and syngas) which can serve as direct energy sources as well as secondary feedstocks for the chemical and petrochemical industry. In this regard, chemical recycling of plastic waste [5,6], anaerobic digestion (AD) of biodegradable organic waste (BOW) [7,8] and carbon dioxide reforming are considered as important processes for reducing the respective fractions of MSW and CO₂ mitigation [9–11].

Food waste (FW), which primarily consists of kitchen waste including raw vegetables, fruits and peels, as well as cooked food waste is a major part of BOW which in turn is often one of the largest components of MSW, being 50 % to 60 % of the total MSW [4,12]. The conventional methods of BOW disposal, e.g. landfilling, composting and

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incineration, are associated with various negative environmental impacts [2,13]. In contrast, AD as waste treatment method offers a more environmentally friendly and economically viable alternative. It not only reduces the negative environmental impact but also produces valuable products that include biogas (renewable energy carrier) and nutrient rich digestate that can be utilized as biofertilizer, thus making it a sustainable waste treatment option [13,14]. AD of organic waste involves the microbial degradation of feedstock that produces biogas consisting mainly of CH₄ (60–70 %) and CO₂ (30–40 %). A wide range of feedstocks, including organic waste, sewage sludge, manure and biomass can be utilized as substrates in AD for biogas production. Among them, BOW/FW stands out due to its high abundance in MSW and its significant content of easily biochemically degradable organic materials, thus making it an attractive feedstock for biogas production via AD [7,8,15,16]. As described above, biogas produced via AD consists primarily of methane and carbon dioxide. Nevertheless, impurities such as hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), siloxanes and ammonia (NH₃) may also be present and need to be removed in order to improve the biogas quality [17–19]. One widely adopted method for biogas cleaning is chemisorption using filter beds containing Fe₂O₃ or Fe(OH)₃, which have gained recognition for their simplicity, high efficiency, and rapid reaction kinetics [20]. At present, biogas production via AD is gaining momentum due to the growing demand for renewable energy and efficient waste management solutions. In 2019, global biogas production reached 62.3 Mm³, with Europe leading the market holding a 50 % share. European biogas plant installations have increased by 20 % annually, primarily driven by the widespread implementation of large-scale industrial facilities [21]. Biogas produced via AD of organic waste is a renewable energy source which can be utilized in various applications. It can be used as a direct fuel for heat and power generation or as a precursor for producing important chemicals such as syngas (a mixture of H₂ and CO), hydrogen and biomethane, which belong to an important group of fuels and intermediates for the chemical industry [22,23].

The first segment of this work deals with biogas production (via AD of FW) and cleaning. The goal was to produce biogas with minimal H₂S content, that can serve as feedstock for the catalytic dry reforming of biomethane, producing syngas. Accordingly, an overview of recent literature on biogas production via AD of FW is given in Table 1. For the present study, AD of FW was carried out in a continuous lab-scale anaerobic reactor and the biogas produced was passed over a chemisorption filter (containing iron hydroxide-based material) for H₂S

removal. The biogas production rate, composition and the effectiveness of the filter bed used is reported.

The second segment of this work deals with syngas production using renewable biogas as feedstock. Syngas (or synthesis gas) is a key intermediate for the chemical industry. It is called synthesis gas because it can be used to synthesize a variety of fuels and chemicals. In industry, the most widely used method for syngas/hydrogen production remains the steam methane reforming (SMR). Unfortunately, SMR due to its reliance on fossil fuels contributes significantly to CO₂ emissions. Therefore, in recent years, there has been a growing interest in hydrogen production through alternative methods [24,25].

In this regard, the so-called dry reforming of methane (DRM) offers an environmentally friendly route for syngas/hydrogen production, as it uses CO₂ in the reforming process. Since DRM is based on the reforming of methane using CO₂ instead of steam, biogas, being renewable and containing both CO₂ and CH₄, presents an ideal feedstock.

The catalytic DRM is highly endothermic and can be described as a two-step reaction. First, methane decomposes on the catalyst surface into active carbon, while hydrogen molecules are released from the surface. In the second step, the active carbon reacts with carbon dioxide molecules to form two carbon monoxide molecules, effectively gasifying the carbon deposits [33].

The selection of an appropriate catalyst is crucial for addressing the challenges associated with DRM, such as catalyst deactivation caused by coke deposition and metal sintering. In literature, both noble metals, such as platinum (Pt), palladium (Pd), rhodium (Rh), and ruthenium (Ru) as well as non-noble metals like nickel (Ni), supported on different materials (e.g. alumina, zeolites, mixed metal oxides etc.) have been studied as catalysts for DRM [34–37]. While Ni-based catalysts, with their medium to medium-high activity, are cost-effective, noble metal catalysts offer significantly enhanced catalytic performance, in terms of coke resistance, stability, and activity. Moreover, incorporating small amounts of noble metals in Ni-based catalysts may improve their overall performance, e.g. a small amount of Rh in Ni-alumina catalyst can enhance the dispersion of Ni particles, preventing sintering and facilitating the CH₄ and CO₂ activation on catalyst surface [38,39].

Since the main aim of this study was to valorize FW into renewable

Table 1

Overview of literature studies on biogas production through anaerobic digestion of food waste (FW).

Feedstock / Substrate	Digestion Temperature (°C)	CO ₂ (vol%)	CH ₄ (vol%)	Impurities in the biogas	H ₂ S trap	Reference
FW	37	35–37	48–54	O ₂	No	Ibro et al., 2025 [26]
FW	25–35	25–50	20–80	*	No	Moffit et al., 2025 [27]
FW	25	70–78	22–30	*	No	Chen et al., 2024 [28]
(potato peel waste)	35	54–69	31–46			
FW (Meat)		24–34	66–76			
FW (Fruit & Veg.)	35	37–46	54–63	*	No	Donatelli & Chang, 2024 [29]
FW (Grain)		36–41	59–64			
FW (Dairy)		26–38	62–74			
FW	21 ± 1	–	55.6 (49–69)	H ₂ S	No	Rusin et al., 2021 [8]
(University canteen)	40 ± 2	–	50–65	H ₂ S		
FW-(Canteen)	15–21	45.3	54.6	H ₂ S, CO	No	Muñoz et al., 2020 [30]
Fine FW (2 mm)	36		67.5 ± 6.9			
Medium FW (4 mm)	36	*	63.7	*	*	Agyeman et al., 2014 [31]
Coarse FW(8 mm)	36		64.2			
FW	37 ± 1	*	30–60	*	*	Kawai et al., 2014 [32]
FW (Canteen)	35	30–65	35–70	H ₂ S	(biofiltration with anaerobic sludge)	Kang et al., 2010 [19]

* Unknown.

Table 2
Overview of literature studies on catalytic dry reforming of biogas for syngas production.

Feedstock	Catalyst	GHSV (mL.h ⁻¹ . g _{catalyst} ⁻¹)	T (°C)	p (atm)	Time (h)	CH ₄ conversion (%)	CO ₂ conversion (%)	H ₂ / CO (-)	Coke deposit (wt%)	Reference
Gas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : N ₂ = 3: 3: 4) Total flowrate = 50 mL.min ⁻¹	3Ni@SiC (423 K) (50 mg)	60,000	650		50	40.9–12.6	54–28.8	0.76 – 0.61	8.9	Shi et al., 2025 [40]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ = 1) Total flowrate = 100 mL.min ⁻¹	5Ni@HZSM-5 ^a (200 mg)	30,000	800	1	24	78–68	85–75	0.82	5	Coelho et al., 2024 [41]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ = 1.5) in Ar Total flowrate = 40 mL.min ⁻¹	11.8 %Ni@La-Ti-p (200 mg)	12,000	800	1	100	57–44	95.2–82.7	1.2	0.9	Veiga et al., 2023 [42]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : Ar = 1: 1: 3) Total flowrate = 100 mL.min ⁻¹	Ni ₁ Co ₁ Mg ₄ Al ₂ (100 mg)	60,000	750	1	12	83	87	0.9	8	Chaghouri et al., 2022 [43]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : N ₂ = 1.5: 1: 7.5) Total flowrate = 100 mL.min ⁻¹	Ni _{67.7} Na ₆ Al _{33.3} (100 mg)	60,000	700	1	8	85–52	90–63	1.5	141.7 ^c	Rosset et al., 2021 [44]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ = 1.5: 1) in N ₂ Total flowrate = 60 mL.min ⁻¹	7 %Ni@CoTiO ₂ (150 mg)	24,000	900	1	15	86.5	91	0.9	25.7	Sharma and Ahir 2020 [45]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ = 1)	10 %Ni-0.5 %Rh@ MgAl ₂ O ₄ (1000 mg)	25,000	800 ^b	5	5	66.1	80	0.9	3	Schiaroli et al., 2019 [39]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ = 1.5:1) Total flow rate: 80 mL.min ⁻¹	12.5 %Ni@ZnAlZr ^d (100 mg)	48,000	750	1	6	40	69	0.97	113.4 ^c	Bezerra et al., 2018 [46]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : N ₂ = 0.4: 0.4: 0.2) no H ₂ S Total flowrate = 40 mL.min ⁻¹					0.833	83	85	0.92	3.28	
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : N ₂ = 0.4: 0.4: 0.2) 100 ppm H ₂ S in N ₂ Total flowrate = 40 mL.min ⁻¹	10 %Ni@SiO ₂ (100 mg)	24,000	750	1	3	5.5	7.9	0.18	e	Chen et al., 2017 [47]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : N ₂ = 0.4: 0.4: 0.2) 50 ppm H ₂ S in N ₂ Total flowrate = 40 mL.min ⁻¹					3.33	6.5	7.5	0.43	e	
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : Ar = 1: 1: 1) Total flowrate = 60 mL.min ⁻¹	5 %Ni@ Mesoporous Alumina (100 mg)	36,000	600	1	4	27–15	42–28	0.55	20	Arbag et al., 2016 [48]
Model biogas mixture (CH ₄ : CO ₂ : He = 1.5: 1: 2.5) Total flowrate = 100 mL.min ⁻¹	8Ni@Al ₂ O ₃ (50 mg) 16Ni@Al ₂ O ₃ (50 mg)	120,000 120,000	800 800	1 1	e e	58.8 67.2	77.3 84.9	0.85 0.93	0.96 e	Goula et al., 2015 [49]

^a Desilicated HZSM-5.

^b Oven Temperature.

^c Calculated from the data as provided by the authors

^d Catalyst reduced at 650 °C.

^e Not specified.

energy carriers (e.g. hydrogen and syngas) by integrating AD and DRM, the second section of the present work is dedicated for the catalytic dry reforming of renewable biogas. Accordingly, an overview of recent literature is given in Table 2.

According to the literature review [50] and the data presented in Table 2, it appears that existing studies on the dry reforming of biogas have been conducted using simulated or model biogas mixtures, typically composed of mixtures of CH_4 and CO_2 as main components. To the best of our knowledge, open literature lacks studies on the dry reforming of real biogas (i.e. sourced directly from anaerobic reactor or biogas production plant/site). In this respect, the goal of the second section of this work was to perform for the first time the catalytic dry reforming of real biogas (sourced from the laboratory anaerobic reactor) over Ni-based catalysts for syngas production to demonstrate the feasibility of the overall process. For this purpose, six catalysts featuring 10 wt% Ni supported on different materials and/or doped with second metal (i.e. Rh and Cu), were selected and synthesized for the catalytic dry reforming of renewable biogas. These catalysts were chosen for their high-performance potential in reforming reactions and their proven activity, as demonstrated in our previous work. The performance of the synthesized catalysts in terms of conversion and stability under different reaction conditions is reported.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Biogas production via AD

2.1.1. Feedstock, inoculum and sorbent

The feedstock for AD consisted of FW collected weekly from the student canteen at the VSB- Technical University of Ostrava (Czech Republic). Prior to processing, all bones were manually removed from the collected samples. Furthermore, in order to reduce compositional variability, the samples were thoroughly mixed into a single homogeneous batch using a grinder (RM Gastro TS-32T400V) fitted with a 6 mm die. The homogenized material was then stored at a temperature of 4–8 °C and re-homogenized prior to each reactor feeding. The inoculum used was obtained from the first stage of a mesophilic agricultural biogas plant (Pustějov II - Zemspol Studénka Ltd., Moravian-Silesian Region, Czech Republic), which utilizes mainly a mixture of corn silage and cattle slurry. The inoculum had a solid content of 7 % by weight and was homogenized using the same method as applied to the feedstock.

The sorbent FERRUM Scon (iron hydroxide-based material with pellet size of 2–4 mm) used to remove H_2S from the raw biogas was purchased from Schaumann BioEnergy Consult GmbH, Germany.

2.1.2. Reactor setup for biogas production and cleaning

The mesophilic AD experiments were carried out in a conventional single-stage vertical continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR) with a working volume of 0.060 m^3 . The CSTR was equipped with a stirrer (operating at 24 RPM) and an electric heating jacket to maintain a stable temperature of 40 ± 0.5 °C, ensuring conditions comparable to those of the biogas plant from which the inoculum was sourced. The reactor was fed with 0.6 kg of homogenized feedstock daily.

During biogas production and collection, H_2S was removed from the product gases through chemisorption. For this purpose, product gases from the anaerobic reactor were passed over a filter bed containing pellets of FERRUM Scon (iron hydroxide-based material). The filter bed consisted of a 50 cm long stainless-steel cylinder with an internal volume of 1 L packed with 500 g of sorbent pellets. After passing through the filter bed, the biogas samples were collected in 100 L Tedlar gas sampling bags for further analysis and processing. A schematic diagram of the setup for biogas production and cleaning is given in Fig. 1 (top).

2.1.3. Biogas analysis

The volume and composition of the biogas produced were determined by using a drum-type gas meter (TG05/PVC/PVC, Ritter,

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the experimental setups used: biogas production via anaerobic digestion of FW (top); catalytic dry reforming of real and model gas mixtures (bottom).

Germany) and a portable biogas analyzer (Biogas 5000, Geotechnical instruments, UK), respectively. The biogas composition was determined daily. The measurements were taken both prior to substrate feeding and during the reactor's operation cycle to monitor fluctuations in the gas composition. The analyzer measured the concentration of major gas components, including CH_4 , CO_2 , as well as the minor components including H_2 , O_2 , and H_2S . Gas concentrations were measured both before and after passing through the desulfurization filter bed to assess the effectiveness of the sorbent for H_2S removal.

2.2. Catalytic dry reforming of model and real biogas mixtures

2.2.1. Feed mixtures

Catalytic dry reforming of real biogas (obtained from the AD of FW)

Table 3

Lists of catalytic materials synthesized.

Catalysts	Synthesis method
10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl ₂ O ₄	Co-precipitation of Hydroxalcalite-type precursors
10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl ₂ O ₄	Co-precipitation of Hydroxalcalite-type precursors
10Ni-MgAl-Silicate	Modified co-precipitation of Hydroxalcalite-type precursors
10Ni-Ce _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} O ₂	Pechini polymerization + Incipient Wetness Impregnation
10Ni-Silicalite-1	Wetness impregnation
10Ni-Al ₂ O ₃	Precipitation method

and model gas mixtures (CH₄ and CO₂) was performed. For all experiments, the CO₂ to CH₄ ratio was kept close to unity. As expected, the CH₄ concentration in the real biogas mixtures was higher than that of the CO₂. Therefore, external CO₂ was added to the real biogas to keep the CO₂ to CH₄ ratio close to one. For the model gas feed, an equimolar flowing mixture of CO₂ and CH₄ was used.

2.2.2. Catalyst synthesis and characterization

For the catalytic dry reforming, a series of catalysts (Table 3) featuring 10 wt% Ni supported on different materials and/or doped with second metal were synthesized. The details of the synthesis procedures adopted for each catalyst sample can be found in the supplementary material.

All catalytic materials were characterized using different methods, namely XRD, H₂-TPR, N₂-physisorption, SEM-EDS and XRF. The details of the measurement methods and the instruments used for XRD, H₂-TPR and N₂-physisorption can be found in references [5, 9], while those for SEM-EDS and XRF are given in [51,52].

2.2.3. Reactor setup for catalytic reforming

All reforming experiments were performed in a lab-scale reactor setup. The schematic representation of the setup is given in Fig.1 (bottom). As shown in the figure, different dosing systems were used for feeding the real and model gas mixtures. In the case of model gas mixtures, the individual gases (i.e. CO₂ and CH₄) from gas bottles were fed to have the desired CO₂ to CH₄ ratio. The flowrates of the gases were regulated with the help of Aalborg GF17 mass flow controllers. As described above, the real biogas samples from the anaerobic digestion plant were collected in 100 L gas sampling bags and mixed with additional CO₂ to adjust the CO₂/CH₄ ratio. In order to feed the real biogas mixtures from 100 L Tedlar bag, a gas pump (SKC Pump TOUCH 220-1000TC-S, USA) was employed.

All reforming experiments were performed in a fixed-bed reactor configuration. The powdered catalyst samples were packed in an 80 cm long quartz tube reactor of 20 mm diameter. The reactor was heated with the help of a tube furnace (LT 50/300/13, LAC, Czech Republic) equipped with a temperature controller. An additional thermocouple was used to determine the temperature of the catalyst bed. The product gases were collected in gas sampling bags and were analyzed using a YL 6100 GC equipped with a ShinCarbon column (micropacked), a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and a flame ionization detector (FID).

2.2.4. Product analysis

The product gas samples were collected in Tedlar gas sampling bags, and the analyses were carried out using an offline GC (YL 6100). The oven temperature program included an isothermal hold at 60 °C for 3 min followed by a ramp of 40 °C/min up to 280 °C. For each injection, a known volume of helium (internal standard) was mixed with the product gas sample in a 50 mL injection syringe.

The CO₂ and CH₄ conversions were calculated using eq. (3) and (4), respectively. The molar ratio H₂/CO was determined by using eqs. (5).

$$X_{CO_2} (\%) = \frac{n_{CO_2,in} - n_{CO_2,out}}{n_{CO_2,in}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$X_{CH_4} (\%) = \frac{n_{CH_4,in} - n_{CH_4,out}}{n_{CH_4,in}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$H_2 / CO = \frac{n_{H_2}}{n_{CO}} \quad (5)$$

where n stands for the total number of moles of respective component.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Biogas production and cleaning

3.1.1. Characterization of FW and sorbent

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and elemental analyses of FW were performed. Based on the TGA results, the value of moisture content (MC), total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS) were found to be 83.94, 16.06 and 15.23 %, respectively. According to the elemental analysis (based on TS) the amounts of C, H, N, S and O were determined as 49.21, 7.49, 1.75, 0.15 and 37.21 wt%, respectively. Further details about the FW and inoculum are given in Table S1 in the supplementary material.

XRD analysis of the fresh and spent sorbent was performed. Iron hydroxide, calcium carbonate and calcium sulphate were determined as main phases present in the samples. XRD diffractograms of the samples and the evaluation data are given in the supplementary material (Fig. S1 and Table S3). The XRF analysis of the spent sorbent showed a significant increase in sulfur content. The details of the elemental analysis of fresh and spent materials are given in the supplementary material (Table S4).

3.1.2. Biogas composition and H₂S removal

The composition of the biogas before (a and b) and after (c and d) the sorption bed (H₂S trap) is given in Fig. 2. The data represents the concentrations measured after feeding the digester with a fresh load of FW. It can be observed that initially, the rates of CH₄ and CO₂ production were similar. However, overtime, the concentration of CH₄ increased while that of CO₂ decreased. These changes are associated with the dynamic processes occurring within the biogas production system. The average values of biogas production rates with respect to TS and VS of FW are given in Table S2 in the supplementary material.

The increase in CH₄ concentration is driven by the growing activity of methanogens, which utilized increased amounts of fresh substrate [53]. The reduction in CO₂ concentration can be attributed to its consumption by hydrogenotrophic methanogens, which use it as a substrate in methane production [54]. Similarly, H₂ exhibited a general decrease in concentration over time. This can be explained by the occurrence of biochemical reactions, such as acetogenesis where hydrogen is consumed by bacteria [55]. In the case of H₂S (Fig. 2b), a systematic reduction in concentration is likely due to the activity of sulfate-reducing bacteria, which convert hydrogen sulfide into less volatile compounds [54].

The H₂S filter demonstrated high efficiency with remarkable stability. It maintained high H₂S removal regardless of temporal variability or inlet gas concentration. In the filter bed, iron hydroxide served as a key component for the effective removal of H₂S from biogas. According to the manufacturer [56], the sorbent material (desulfurizer: FERRUM Scon) removes H₂S in two steps (Eqs. 6 and 7).

Iron hydroxide reacts with H₂S to form ferric sulfide. The ferric sulfide produced during this process can be regenerated back into ferric hydroxide and elemental sulfur by exposing it to air or oxygen.

The moisture content in the raw and filtered biogas was determined by using a SENSIDYNE detection system with precision gas detector sorption tube no. 177SA. A noticeable reduction in moisture content of the biogas (from approximately 3.3 to 2.5 %) was observed after passing over the sorbent bed. This decrease is likely due to the adsorption processes occurring within the sorbent bed.

Fig. 2. Composition of biogas before (a and b) and after (c and d) H₂S removal.

Table 4

Properties of the catalysts employed for the present study.

Catalyst	Ni content* (wt%)	H ₂ consumption during TPR (mmol/g)	S _{BET} (m ² /g)
10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl ₂ O ₄	10.5	1.626	75
10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl ₂ O ₄	10.8	1.559	98
10Ni-MgAl-Silicate	11.1	1.551	96
10Ni-Ce _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} O ₂	10	2.393	14
10Ni-Silicalite-1	12.4	1.655	332
10Ni-Al ₂ O ₃	9.1	1.655	69

* Determined by XRF.

3.2. Dry reforming of model and real biogas mixtures over Ni-based catalysts

3.2.1. Characterization of catalysts

A series of six catalysts were synthesized for the catalytic dry reforming. All samples were characterized by XRD, SEM, XRF, H₂-TPR and N₂-physorption. The results are given in Table 4, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

As shown in Table 4, the amount of H₂ consumed by all catalysts subjected to TPR characterization matched quite well the theoretical value of 1.704 mmol. g⁻¹, except for 10Ni-Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂. In agreement with previous literature [57,58], in this case the onset of the reduction in catalyst was as low as 200 °C, because the Ni²⁺ is not exsolved, but instead is easily accessible on catalyst surface, and in the form of easily reducible NiO. The main reduction peak is centered around 360 °C but

Fig. 3. H₂-TPR profiles of the catalysts employed.

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of all catalysts (with NiO phase marked) along with SEM-EDS mapping.

the presence of a shoulder at 395 °C strongly suggests the occurrence of a metal-support interaction [59,60] (e.g., H₂ spillover from Ni nanoparticles to the surface of the support) that results in the reduction of surface Ce species. A roughly stable H₂ consumption continued up to 900 °C leading to a very broad peak; the latter consumption was attributed to the reduction of the bulk of ceria-zirconia support. Also in this case Ni⁽⁰⁾ is likely to be involved in a spillover effect, in analogy with similar results obtained with Rh/CZO catalyst [61].

The results of XRD and SEM-EDS analysis are given in Fig. 4. The powder XRD diffractogram of the 10Ni—Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ sample showed the typical pattern of the ceria-zirconia solid solution plus that of nickel oxide. The successful formation of the desired Ce/Zr mixed oxide was confirmed by the observed 2θ values (i.e., 29.3, 33.9, 48.7, 57.8, 60.6, 71.1, 78.8) [61,62], which are shifted toward higher angles (= lower interplanar distances) in respect to those expected from cerianite (cubic, fluorite-type, pure CeO₂), due to the partial substitution of the bulkier Ce⁴⁺ (0.97 Å) with the smaller Zr⁴⁺ (0.89 Å), as can be observed in Fig. S2.

The diffractogram of 10Ni-MgAl-Silicate was quite complex due to the presence of several distinct crystal phases. It was characterized by the presence of three families of reflexes: the former group is characterized by sharper reflexes attributable to a forsterite-like phase (Ni_xMg_{2-x}SiO₄) [63,64] the second is characterized by a small group of broad reflexes attributable to a periclase-like (Ni_xMg_{1-x}O) phase [63,64]; the latter is the less abundant spinel phase (Ni_xMg_{1-x}Al₂O₄) [63,64]. The calcination of carbonates-intercalated LDHs results in the formation of mixed metal oxides usually with high specific surface area (SSA) due to the decomposition of interlayer carbonates into CO₂ and loss of interlayer water and hydroxide groups [63]. However, calcination temperature as high as 900 °C may lead to decrease in SSA due to the formation of a mixture of MgO and the spinel MgAl₂O₄, in which Ni

is homogeneously distributed in a solid solution. On the other hand, silicates do not decompose into volatile species, therefore when they are present as the interlayer anions the collapse of the LDH crystal structure results in the formation of a mixture of Ni-substituted periclase and Ni-substituted forsterite, thus limiting the incorporation of Ni in the spinel phase. As expected from previous literature [63,64], the TPR profile for this material was characterized by an onset temperature around 650–700 °C, and a H₂ consumption continuing up to 900 °C, confirming that the exsolution of γ-Al₂O₃ and forsterite (Ni_xMg_{2-x}SiO₄) phases calcined at 900 °C requires very high temperatures.

The catalyst that exhibited the highest specific surface area was Ni-silicalite-1. The corresponding XRD pattern revealed the presence of distinct silicalite-1 and NiO phases. In this case, the NiO reduction profile was centred at around 395 °C, likely associated to a higher dispersion of this phase over the catalyst surface if compared to 10Ni—Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ sample. The XRD pattern of Ni-Al₂O₃ showed peaks characteristics of γ-Al₂O₃, along with reflections attributed to NiO, slightly shifted toward higher 2θ values. This shift suggests either a strong interaction between NiO and the support or the partial formation of a solid solution between the two phases (Ni_{1-x}Al_xO). This interpretation is further supported by the occurrence of several additional low-intensity peaks, possibly related to the formation of spinel-like phase such as NiAl₂O₄. In this context, the heterogenous distribution of Ni-species within the oxide matrix aligns with the H₂-TPR profile, which displays a broad reduction peak starting around 320 °C and extending up to 700 °C, likely corresponding to the reduction of both readily available NiO and Ni species strongly interacting with Al₂O₃. The analyses conducted on the 10Ni0.5Rh/Cu-MgAl₂O₄ catalysts revealed nearly identical XRD patterns, characterized by the peaks attributable to the formation of two solid solutions: Ni_xMg_{1-x}O and Ni_xMg_{1-x}Al₂O₄ [39].

Due to the low content of Cu and Rh in the catalyst formulation, no crystalline phases containing these elements were detected. The strong interaction between Ni species and Mg/Al/O matrix is further reflected in the TPR profiles, which exhibit a similar reduction behavior with an H_2 consumption peak centered around $860^\circ C$, indicating enhanced thermal stability of these Ni-species toward reduction.

The SEM-EDS mapping, showing the distribution of all relevant elements for each catalyst sample, confirmed a homogenous distribution of the phases without evidencing any significant micro-segregation of the elements after calcination. It is worth noting that the 10Ni- Al_2O_3 deviates from this general trend, showing clear signs of a heterogeneous distribution of Ni, clearly visible in the EDS maps in Fig. 4.

3.2.2. Catalyst screening

In the first phase of the experimental campaign of catalytic dry reforming, screening tests were carried out. For this purpose, all catalysts were tested at three different temperatures i.e. 750 , 800 and $850^\circ C$ using constant GHSV i.e. $12,000 mL.h^{-1}.g_{catalyst}^{-1}$ and employing both model and real biogas (after H_2S removal and adjusting the CH_4/CO_2 ratio) mixtures as feed. The main reactions during dry reforming of methane are given in eqs. 8, 9 and 10.

The results obtained for the model gas mixtures are shown in Fig. 5 (a and b) and those for the real biogas mixtures in Fig. 5. (c and d). For both feed mixtures, a similar behavior in terms of CO_2 and CH_4 conversion was shown by four Ni catalysts that featured oxides and silicate of Mg and Al and/or doped with a second metal. This indicates that for these 4 catalysts, the presence of a small amount of H_2O and other trace compounds (not determined) in real biogas mixtures affected the conversions only slightly.

The Ni catalysts supported on silicalite-1 and on oxides of Ce and Zr however gave significantly lower conversions for model gas mixtures

which were further decreased when the real biogas mixtures were employed. Please note that in the present study, impurities other than H_2S (e.g. ammonia or siloxanes), which may be present in the real biogas, were not analyzed. Their presence could potentially influence catalyst performance during the DRM reaction. To further purify the biogas, the concentration and types of these impurities may be assessed by GC-MS analysis, and appropriate cleaning steps could be implemented accordingly.

Considering the performance during the screening tests, Ni catalysts featuring oxides and silicates of Mg and Al were chosen for the long-term experiments for which the results are given in the next section.

3.2.3. Conversion and selectivity during long-term tests

Based on the results of screening tests, four catalysts i.e.

Fig. 5. Performnce of all catalysts during the screening tests performed at different temperatures on model and real biogas mixtures using the GHSV of $12,000 mL.h^{-1}.g_{catalyst}^{-1}$.

10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄, 10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl₂O₄, 10Ni-MgAl-silicate and 10Ni-Al₂O₃ were chosen for the long-term tests. All experiments for the long-term tests were performed at 750 °C using 0.5 g of catalyst samples with a gas hourly space velocity of 36,000 mL.h⁻¹.g_{catalyst}⁻¹. Each experiment on individual catalyst was carried out for a total of 15-h time on stream, spread over 2 days. After the end of the first day, the reactor was purged with Ar and cooled to room temperature under constant flow of Ar. The next day, the reactor was heated to the reaction temperature under Ar flow and fed with the desired feed mixture either model or real biogas. At the end of each test the spent catalyst was characterized by TEM-EDS and TGA. The details of the measurement method and instrument used for TEM-ESD can be found in [65]. The TGA was performed using a TG analyzer Hitachi STA300 (Hitachi Japan). For the TG analysis, about 10 mg spent catalyst sample was heated in air to 900 °C

using a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

The performance of all catalysts in terms of CO₂ and CH₄ conversions, syngas yield, H₂ to CO ratio and coke formation rate is given in Fig. 6. From the results, it can be observed that the catalyst 10Ni-Rh-MgAl₂O₄ outperformed the rest in all aspects.

The gradual increase in CO₂ and CH₄ conversion on day 1 and 2 in this case can be ascribed to the progressive (in-situ) reduction of the active phase during the reaction that led to higher conversions with time. Please note that regardless of their different reduction behavior shown in H₂-TPR (Fig. 3), all catalysts were reduced and activated at the same temperature (i.e., at the reaction temperature of 750 °C using 50 % H₂ in Ar) prior to the respective experiment. Since Rh doped catalyst exhibited the reduction peak during H₂-TPR at higher temperature (Fig. 3), it is assumed that it was not completely reduced during the

Fig. 6. CO₂ and CH₄ conversion (a and b respectively) at 750 °C with GHSV of 36,000 mL.h⁻¹.g_{catalyst}⁻¹, syngas yield (c), H₂/CO ratio (d), TGA of spent catalysts (e) and rate of coke formation (f).

reduction and activation step which was performed at 750 °C. Therefore, the catalyst underwent progressive reduction and activation during the reaction which resulted in increased conversions with time.

A similar behavior can be seen in the case of Cu doped catalyst that exhibited similar reduction behavior as compared to the Rh doped catalyst. The conversions in the case of the Cu doped sample however were lower than those shown by Rh containing sample. The phenomenon of progressive reduction during the reaction is less pronounced in the case of 10Ni-MgAl-Silicate that showed the reduction peak at comparatively lower temperature as compared to both Rh and Cu containing samples.

For the day 2 operations with real biogas mixture, the catalysts have shown a slight decrease in CO₂ conversion. One of the contributing factors for this behavior can be the occurrence of water gas shift reaction (reaction III in eq. 10) that partially consumed CO in the presence of water (in the case of real biogas mixture) to produce CO₂. This increased the CO₂ concentration in the product gases, thereby decreasing the global conversion of CO₂ and increasing the H₂/CO ratio accordingly. A similar catalyst behavior in the presence of water was reported by Eltejaei et al., [66]. Moreover, in addition to the presence of moisture, the common trace compound (not determined in the present work) in the biogas might also have contributed to the slight decrease in the CO₂ conversion.

10Ni-Al₂O₃ sample showed the lowest activity, giving CO₂ and CH₄

conversions of around 70 % and 50 %, respectively together with a low H₂/CO ratio of ≈ 0.7 , likely due to a stronger contribution of the reverse water-gas shift reaction on this support [67]. It is noteworthy that, after only a few hours of operation, the use of this catalyst led to a significant increase in reactor pressure, ultimately causing the premature termination of the analysis of reaction products. This phenomenon was attributed to extensive carbon formation in reaction conditions, as confirmed from TG analysis of the spent catalyst (Fig. 6e, f). The deposited carbon likely covered the active surface and contributed to reactor blockage, resulting in an increased pressure drop along the catalyst bed.

In this context, Mg-containing samples showed a significantly lower carbon formation, likely related to the presence of surface basic sites [39] and to a stronger metal support interaction as evidenced from the high-temperature NiO reduction peak registered during H₂-TPR analyses (Fig. 3). Among these catalysts, the 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄ sample exhibited the lowest amount of carbon deposition rate under dry reforming conditions, reaching a value below 2.5 mg g_{catalyst}⁻¹ h⁻¹, approximately an order of magnitude lower than that observed for 10Ni-Al₂O₃.

The TEM analyses of the spent catalysts confirmed the substantial carbon accumulation (Fig. 7d) of the latter sample, revealing the extensive presence of both long carbon nanotubes spanning several hundred nanometers (20–50 nm wide) and thin graphitic layers

Fig. 7. STEM-HAADF images and relative distributions of the metal particles after reaction for 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄ (a), 10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl₂O₄ (b), 10Ni-MgAl-Silicate (c) and 10Ni-Al₂O₃ (d).

encapsulating the formed Ni particles (likewise detectable on 10Ni-MgAl-Silicates). It is worth noting that carbon was visible also for the other samples tested (Fig. S3), albeit to different extents in accordance with TG analyses, and was mainly present in the form of filamentous coke (that in some cases caused the detachment of Ni particles from the surface) or free amorphous carbon, whose occurrence was significantly reduced in the 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄ sample. From the analysis of the metal particle size distributions (performed over 200 particles for each sample) after the reaction, it was possible to establish a clear correlation between the observed catalytic activity and both the average diameter and size distribution of the active phase nanoparticles. 10Ni-Al₂O₃ catalyst was characterized by a wide distribution of Ni-particles whose diameter spanned from 4 to 80 nm (mean size of 24 nm). Although the occurrence of sintering phenomena involving the active phase during reaction cannot be ruled out, it is interesting to note that the results appear to reflect the heterogeneous distribution of different Ni-species in the calcined sample, as evidenced by XRD and consistently with its broad reduction profile (Fig. 3–4). The comparable activity registered between 10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl₂O₄ and 10Ni-MgAl₂O₄-Silicates catalysts is

reflected in similar particles' average size of 10 nm and 11 nm, respectively, with only rare, isolated aggregates exceeding 40 nm of diameter for both samples. Despite the similar average sizes, a more detailed analysis of the distributions reveals that the Cu-containing catalyst exhibits a significantly higher fraction of smaller particles, with ~72 % of the active sites below 10 nm. In contrast, the silicates-based sample shows only 47 % of particles within the same size range. This difference can be ascribed to the bimetallic nature of 10Ni–Cu0.5-MgAl₂O₄ catalyst, which led to the formation of a Ni–Cu alloy, as evidenced through TEM-EDS analyses of different particles after reaction (Fig. S4), that in agreement with previous literature [68,69], improved the dispersion of the active phase during activation/reaction. Similarly, it was found that the 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄ catalyst, which exhibited the highest catalytic activity among all tested systems, was characterized by the presence of highly dispersed Ni–Rh bimetallic nanoparticles. This resulted in the narrowest particle size distribution, with an average diameter of 5 nm, likely stabilized by the formation of a Ni–Rh alloy, with size-dependent variations in the Ni/Rh atomic ratio observed among the analyzed particles (Fig. S5) [65]. It is noteworthy that the

Fig. 8. Stability test of the catalyst 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄: CO₂ and CH₄ conversion and H₂/CO (top); TGA of the spent catalyst and the rate of coke formation (bottom).

evidence for the formation of such alloy further supports the improved resistance to carbon deposition observed for this catalyst (Fig. 6f). As reported in previous studies, the synergy between these two metals, particularly the presence of Rh in the alloy, effectively inhibits the growth of carbon, also due to the promotion of an alternative mechanism for CH₄ adsorption and decomposition [39,70].

3.2.4. Stability test

The best performing catalyst (10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄) in the long-term experiments was further tested for its stability during online change of reaction parameters, such as temperature and GHSV. For the experiment, a 0.5 g of fresh catalyst sample was used that was reduced and activated at 800 °C. The reaction temperature and GHSV were varied as depicted in Fig. 8 (top). The experiment was performed for over 30 h time on stream spread over several days. At the end of each day, the reactor was cooled to room temperature and the next day heated up to the reaction temperature under a constant flow of Ar, and no regeneration of the catalyst was performed during the whole experiment. From the results as shown in Fig. 8 (top), it can be observed that the catalyst showed an excellent stability and robustness during the experiment. It maintained its high performance, even with high fluctuations in the reaction condition.

It is to be noted that at 750 °C and GHSV of 36,000 mL.h⁻¹.g_{catalyst}⁻¹, the catalyst gave somewhat higher conversions than those reported in section 3.2.3. This may be caused by the different pretreatment (i.e. reduction at 800 °C) of the catalyst employed for the stability test as compared to the samples used in the previous section where the catalyst reduction was performed at 750 °C. The results of TGA as shown in Fig. 8 (bottom) indicate that the catalyst produced minimal coke as compared to other catalysts even serving for longer time on stream.

4. Conclusion and outlook

This work was dedicated to food waste (FW) valorization into renewable energy carriers by combining anaerobic digestion (AD), desulphurization of the resulting biogas, and inline dry reforming (DRM) of the desulphurized real biogas. Although the latter process has been intensively investigated in several studies, it is important to note that none of those studies used the real biogas (sourced from anaerobic reactor or biogas plant/site); instead, they employed simulated or model biogas, typically composed of mixtures of CH₄ and CO₂ as main components.

In the first segment of this work, the AD of FW was carried out in a lab-scale anaerobic reactor to produce biogas. Considering that sulfur is a well-known poison for reforming catalysts (e.g., Ni, Rh etc.), the issue of the presence of hydrogen sulfide in the produced biogas was addressed by applying a cleaning method based on the chemisorption of H₂S. It was shown that iron hydroxide-based materials are effective sorbents to remove hydrogen sulfide from biogas through chemisorption.

In the second segment of this work, the previously produced and desulphurized biogas was upgraded to syngas by means of DRM. The reforming experiments were carried out over six Ni-based catalysts featuring different support materials. As feedstocks, both model gas (mixture of pure CO₂ and CH₄) and desulphurized real biogas mixed with external CO₂ were used, while keeping the CO₂/CH₄ ratios close to one in all cases. Ni-based catalyst doped with Rh and supported on mixed oxides of magnesium and aluminum outperformed all tested catalysts in terms of carbon dioxide and methane conversion. The formation of stable and highly dispersed Ni–Rh nanoparticles assured the highest syngas yield among all catalysts tested with minimum coke formation during operation. Moreover, this catalyst showed outstanding stability and robustness for 34 h of time-one-stream, effectively maintaining high performance despite online changes in the reaction parameters.

Summing up, due to its abundance in MSW, FW is an attractive

feedstock to produce renewable biogas through AD. Once the problem of sulfur is addressed, renewable biogas becomes an excellent feedstock for producing syngas via DRM. With renewable and carbon neutral biogas as feedstock, DRM becomes a viable process to produce renewable energy carriers and can potentially play a key role in future carbon-neutral energy systems. A combination of AD and DRM thus presents a promising opportunity to recycle biodegradable waste (BOW) and CO₂, while producing cleaner fuels. In this regard, the present study may provide new insights into the development of sustainable catalytic processes that simultaneously reduce both BOW and CO₂ emissions, while producing valuable products.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Amer Inayat: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petra Wojnarova:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Piotr Jachimowicz:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jacopo De Maron:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Elisabetta Orfei:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nicola Schiaroli:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Carlo Lucarelli:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Kamil Gorecki:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Francesco Basile:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Pavel Lestinsky:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Jiri Rusin:** Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Francesco Basile has patent #WO 2004 108,276 A1 issued to Air Liquide. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2025.108348>.

Data availability

The data is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/15719085>; DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15719084.

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